

Review Article

The Haemostatic Effect of Jati Patra Swaras In Sravi Arsha

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ABSTRACT

Raktarsha, is a vital disease and at rest a challenge to the medical field.. In Ayurveda, lots of provision and drugs are described as a Rakta stambhak in the management of Raktarsha, Raktapitta, Raktatisar etc. but there are hardly any researches on assessment of haemostatic properties of drugs. So there is an imperative need to have gaze on the subject and innovate medicine which will provide comparatively victorious and suitable for the management of Raktarsha. In the present study, the efforts are made to assess the haemostatic effect of Jati patra Swaras in Raktarsha,. As being a pilot study, results are not assessed on the standard parameters. RCT (Randomized Control Trial) can be conducted to compare effectiveness of Jati patra Swaras with many other haemostatic drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Sravi Arsha or Raktarsha is a bleeding pile which occurs due to the dominance of Pitta and Rakta. Bleeding piles is a very common disease of alimentary canal in India which can affect both male and female. It is a condition in which patient passes suddenly streaks of bright red blood with

stool. Sometimes it may bleed profusely leading to the most common complication like Anemia. Due to the high prevalence rate, many efforts have been made to come up with a wide spectrum treatment modalities. As mentioned in Ayurvedic texts, Jati patra Swaras has an important place. According to

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Ayurveda, Jati patra Swaras is Katu and Kashay rasatmak and exerts antiseptic, haemostatic, astringent, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory & antibacterial effect on human beings. It has various external as well as internal applications to cure wound and many other diseases. Based on these references, a pilot study is conducted to evaluate the haemostatic effect of Jati patra Swaras in Sravi Arsha.

A clinical study is conducted on the well diagnosed patients of Sravi Arsha. Patients were diagnosed on the basis of 7 International Criteria for Hemorrhoids- Bleeding, Pain, Difficulty in passing stool, Protrusion, Confirmatory tests like DRE and Proctoscopy. Patients attending the OPD and IPD of Dr.D.Y.Patil College Of Ayurved & Research Centre, Pimpri, Pune.

Inclusive criteria:

Well diagnosed adult patients of bleeding piles between the ages of 20 to 50 years with Grade I to III were included in the present study.

Exclusive Criteria:

Patients suffering from other systemic diseases like HT, HIV, CA, HbsAg positive patients, children and pregnant women were excluded from the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

Materials used for the present study were **Jati patra Swaras 20 ml** sterile water ampoules, 20 ml Disposable syringes with rubber tubes, lithotomic table, patients attending the OPD and IPD of Dr.D.Y.Patil College Of Ayurved & Research Centre, Pimpri ,Pune.

METHODS

Total 30 adult patients were selected randomly irrespective of age, sex, caste, creed religion and occupation. After giving idea of the treatment and taking well informed written consent, patients were divided equally into 2 groups of each 15 patients by alternate method.

Group A:

Group A was given standard Ayurvedic medicinal treatment.

Group B:

Group B was treated with 20 ml **Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras 20 ml per anal** along with standard. Ayurvedic medicinal treatment for consecutive 10 days. Assessment of the signs and symptoms was done before and after the treatment. Patients asked to come daily for follow up for clinical assessment up to 10 days.

Assessment of the signs and symptoms was done on the basis of international criteria for Sravi Arsha.

1. Bleeding per Anal in group A (A group with standard Ayurvedic Treatment): Patient No./Day of Treatment 1st 2nd 3rd 4th 5th 6th 7th 8th 9th 10th

Patient No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	++++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	+	-	-
2	++++	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	+	-	-
3	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	-
4	++++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	-
5	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	-
6	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	+	+	-
7	++++	+++	++	+++	++	++	+	+	+	-
8	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	+	+	-
9	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	+	+	+	-
10	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	+	-
11	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	+	--

12	++++	++++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	+	+
13	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	-
14	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	+	-
15	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	+	--

2. Bleeding per Anal in group B (Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras 20 ml per anal along with standard Ayurvedic treatment): Patient No./ Day of Treatment 1st 2nd 3rd 4th 5th 6th 7th 8th 9th 10th

Patient No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	++++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	-	-	-
2	++++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	-	-	-
3	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-
4	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	+	-	-	-
5	+++	+++	++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-
6	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	-	-	-
7	++++	+++	++	+++	++	+	-	-	-	-
8	+++	+++	+++	++	++	+	-	-	-	-
9	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	-	-	-	-
10	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	+	-	-	-
11	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	+	-	-	--
12	++++	++++	+++	+++	++	+	+	-	-	
13	+++	+++	++	++	+	+	-	-	-	-
14	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	+	-	-	-
15	++++	+++	+++	+++	++	+	-	-	-	--

- +: Mild bleeding with less than 10 drops/Occasionally between 2 to 3 days
- ++: Mild bleeding with 10 to 30 drops in each defecation.
- +++: Stream/ more than 50 drops in each Defecation

OBSERVATIONS

It was observed that the patients from group B got maximum relief from bleeding within the short period of 3 to 4 days than the patients from group A. Also pain, difficulty in passing stool, pruritus, mucosal discharge and degree of prolapsed reduced drastically in group B which was given **Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras 20 ml per anal** for successive 10 days along with standard herbal medicinal treatment.

DISCUSSION

Table no.1,2 shows that experimental group results were more significant than the control group. Trial drugs has following properties:

Jatipatra: Uses: Kashayras katu vipaki shitivrya best Vranpropak and raktastambhak

Thus, the study shows that **Jati patra Swaras** is an effective local haemostatic agent in controlling bleeding piles. **Jati patra Swaras** exerts its astringent and haemostatic effect through a chemical reaction with blood proteins which results in controlling the bleeding. It is safe, cost effective and easily reached way to seize the bleeding.

Discussion on apparent mode of action of Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras 20 ml per anal.

From above discussion we can go over the main points to that **Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras** formulation relief symptoms of Bleeding piles i.e. regulates bowel habit, improving digestion, control of pain, Itching and shrinkage of pile mass which is due to Vranropan. In this way **Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras** formulation in

management of Sravi Arsha acts as a multi dimensional approach by providing relief from symptom in the patients suffering from Sravi Arsha.

RESULTS

The total effect **Matra basti of Jati patra Swaras 20 ml per anal** in bleeding piles was adequately found to be vastly considerable over the standard Ayurvedic medicinal treatment.

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